

Sharia and Conventional National Pension Savings Bank (BTPN): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

M. Ilyas Mawardi, Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi

Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, Indonesia

wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to map research topics around BTPN Syariah and Conventional on Islamic Financial Inclusion with a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key words " BTPN Syariah and Conventional " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around BTPN Syariah and Conventional based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 6 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Sharia and Conventional BPTN, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing credit products; (5) Savings products; and (6) Other issues. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding BTPN Syariah and Conventional, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: BTPN Syariah and Conventional; Islamic Financial Inclusion; Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

Banks are known as financial institutions which have activities to accept checking deposits, savings and deposits. According to Republic of Indonesia Law Number 10 of 1998 concerning banking which states " Banks are business entities that collect funds from the public in the form of savings and distribute them to the public in the form of credit or other forms in order to improve the standard of living of many people". Therefore, A bank is a company that has a role in the financial sector.

In Indonesia, there are two types of banks, namely conventional banks and sharia banks. The legal basis comes from Bank Indonesia Regulations, which are used as the basis for decision making. Such as the revised BI Regulation number 17/12/PBI/2015 which contains the obligation to provide credit by commercial banks to MSMEs. BTPN Syariah and Conventional have an important role in supporting financing in the form of micro businesses and special financing for women in terms of productive poverty.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding BTPN Syariah and Conventional uses library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding BTPN Syariah and Conventional, so that

it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding BTPN Syariah and Conventional, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

BTPN Bank has 2 types, namely BTPN Syariah and Conventional. BTPN Conventional is a bank that provides services to retirees and active employees. Meanwhile, BTPN Syariah is a subsidiary of BTPN which has share ownership of 70% and is the only bank that serves the people's business segment. BTPN Syariah was founded in 1991 as a result of an acquisition from PT Bank Sahabat Purba Danarta and has a non-bank license. Apart from that, BTPN Syariah is also based on several laws such as Law Number 21 of 2008 National Pension Savings Bank (BTPN)

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in

bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The research object is BTPN Syariah and Conventional. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about BTPN Syariah and Conventional. The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key words " BTPN Syariah and Conventional " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around BTPN Syariah and Conventional based on the journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

In this chapter, we will discuss research mapping related to Bank BTPN Syariah and Conventional using the VOSviewer bibliometric method and Library Research. Based on search results on the Garuda website (Digital Referral Garba), we found data on scientific articles from 60 journals that have been nationally accredited.

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications About Bank BTPN Syariah and Conventional

The results of a search for article publications on the Garuda website (Digital Referral Group) regarding BTPN Syariah and Conventional Banks from 2015 to 2022 show that 60 journals have been published. Judging from the number of publications for BTPN Syariah and Conventional Bank research, it can be seen that the number of publications continues to increase every year. 2021 will be the year with the highest number of publications, namely 13 articles in one year. This figure is the highest number of publications in 9 years. So, the average number of article publications regarding Bank BTPN Syariah and Conventional is 6 articles per year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Bank BTPN Syariah and Conventional by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2015	1	2019	11
2016	4	2020	11

2017	2	2021	13
2018	8	2022	10
Total 60			

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2010.

In table 2, there is data on the names of affiliates/institutions with the number of publications related to Bank BTPN Syariah and Conventional research. Innovative Learning Journal is the name of the affiliate/institution that publishes the most research in 3 journals regarding Bank BTPN Syariah and Conventional.

Table 2. Affiliates/institutions publishing journals regarding Bank BTPN Syariah and Conventional

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Journal of Innovative Learning	3
BBM (Bulletin of Business & Management), e_Scientific Journal of Accounting Research, JOURNAL OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION, Journal of Business Administration, Journal of Islamic Economics and Business, Journal of Management Science	2
Accounting Global Journal, Ahkam: Journal of Islamic Law, Aisyah Journal of Informatics and Electrical Engineering (AJIEE), Al-Akhbar, Al-bank Journal of Islamic Banking and Finance, Al-Iqtishad Journal of Sharia Economics, AL-MANHAJ: Journal of Law and Islamic Social Institutions, AMALIAH: JOURNAL OF COMMUNITY SERVICE, AT-TASYRI: SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF MUAMALAH PRODI, Business UHO: Journal of Business Administration, DYNAMICS: Journal of Accounting Management, Business and Entrepreneurship, E-JRM: Electronic Journal of Management Research, eBa Journal: Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting, Economics & Business, EKSYA: Journal of Sharia Economics, El-Qist: Journal of Islamic Economics and Business (JIEB), Exacta Factors, FOKUS Journal of Islamic and Social Studies, Growth, JAK (Junal of Accounting) Scientific Studies Accounting, JAMMIAH (Scientific Journal of Islamic Economics Students), JIMF (Scientific Journal of Forkamma Management), Journal of Management and Business Innovations, Journal of Business Administration, Journal of Assets: Accounting and Financial Research, Journal of National Development Economics, Journal of Co Management, Journal of Digit, Journal of Contemporary Economics and Business, Journal of the Kuningan Faculty of Islamic Sciences, Indonesian Accounting Scientific Journal, Scientific Journal of Islamic Economics, Scientific Journal of Accounting Economics Students, Journal of Islamic Economics and Business, Journal of Management Science, Journal of Community Innovation, ISLAMIKA JURNAL, MEBIS JURNAL (Management and Business), Mediasociation Journal, Innovative Learning	1

Journal, Syntax Admiration Journal, Collection of Law Faculty Student Journals, Liquidity, Accounting and Management Research Journal, MABIS: Journal of Sharia Business Management, Maliyah: Journal of Islamic Business Law, Maqdis: Journal of Islamic Economic Studies, Maro: Journal of Sharia Economics and Business, Owner: Research and Accounting Journal, REVITALIZATION: Journal of Management Science, STAR, Syntax Lirate, Tasharruf: Journal of Economics and Business of Islam, VALUE

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2010.

Table 3 shows the most productive researcher, namely Trimulato, who wrote 4 journal articles.

Table 3. Productivity of researchers around Bank BTPN Syariah and Conventional

Researcher	Number of Publications
Trimulato	4
Muhammadsjah, Anggiearanidipta Suma	2
Alfiandi, Damsar Damsar, Yurri Trinanda; Amalia, Amalia; Amaliah, Siti Kustinah, Lisna; Anita, Siska Yuli; Anjar K, Wahyudi; Artha, M Ardi Nupi Hasyim, Widya Astuti, Nurul Fadhila, Sukma Jaya; Astuti, Hamidah Nayati Utami, Okky Sandy Pranata, Endang Siti; Athia, Denis Apriliyanto, Nur Hidayati, Ita; Ayu Franita Putri Maria Ulfa KN; Daud, Zata Ghaisani Mazaya, Ruflah M; Effendy Ellys, Wulandari, Shara, Harahap, Lily Rahmawati, RY, Thoyib; Faizah, Muhammad Iqbal Surya Pratikto, Helmina Ardyanfitri, Enha Arini; Fitri, Mirawati Mirawati, Rahmad Ade Putra, Meli Diana; Hasanah, Farhan Lauda, Resfa Fitri, Qoriatul; Hatta, Amelia Nurqoidah Sudrajat1, Lena Magdalena, Muhammad; Hidayat, Efi Elmi Fitri Siregar, Della Hilia Anriva, Muhammad; Hosen, Reni Kristiana Ashuri, Muhammad Nadrattuzaman; Ijtihadi, Noviendri Djalil, Andreas Rafael, Bahrul Rohman, Iswandi Iswandi, Wawan Santoso, Arif Safari, Ahmad Fakih; Ikhsan Rahmani Timorita, Ainul, Yulianti; Irsan, Muhammad; Junaidi, Khamidatul Azizah, Arifudin Arifudin, Junaidi; Karolina, Anum Nuryani, Karo, Ina; Khodijah, Siti; Kholijah, Pitriani Gultom, Siti; Lestari, Rinto Alexandro, Endah Ayu; Lestari, Sri Gisa Anggraeni, Ayu Gumilang; Mardianti Ajeng, Artie, Hasna Nabila; Mawardi, Siti Hakimatun Nisak, Moh. Amin, M Cholid; Mulyadi S.Pd, Rahmi Citra Lestari, M.Pd, Kunto Imbar Nursetyo; Munira, M.Ag; Muzajjad, Henny Dwijayani, Suhartatik, Rubait Dasururi, Ach; Muzayyanah Nurazizah, Muzayyanah, Nurazizah; Ningsih, Muhammad Iqbal, Nur Wahyu; Nurliawati, Vina Andita Pratiwi, Lia; Final, Dwi Ratna; Pandansari, Rekyan; Pertiwi, EKA Mega; Purnama, Ajeng Rezkita Suci, Dewi Nurapiyah, Yulia; Daughter, Husni Shabri, Meidya; Rahmayanti, Mugi Juwita, Rima; Rakhmah, Pedagogita; Riati, Alvien Nur Amalia, Lisa Aprin; Ridwan, Elly Herawati,	1

Fachriana Ulfatun; Rumiasih, Desmy Riani, Denia Maulani, Dewi Megawati, Hannisa Rahmani, Puspita Sari, NA; Rusmiyati, Viddy Cariesty Genoveva, E Mulya Syamsul, Kurnia; S, Riska Ayu Pramesti, Dian Amorina; Safitri, Nuri; Septyana, Agus Yudianto, Tika Indah; Suminar, Mira Veranita, Suminar; Supeni Rayna Rika, Retno Endah, Ruspita; Supriyani, Dicky Fauzi Firdaus, Imam Dwi Putranto, Euis; Veni, Aqwa Naser Daulay, Fauzi Arif Lubis, Dea Lora; Vio Narakusuma Ardayani, Putu, Jati, I Ketut; Wahyuni, Trimulato, Andi Zulfikar Darussalam, Syarifuddin, Sri; Warso, Muhamad Ali Mukhson, Maria Magdalena, Moh Mukeri; Widiana, I Nyoman Wahyu, Sudiana, I Ketut; Yudianto Tika Indah, Agus, Septyana.

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2010

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on BTPN Syariah and Conventional Banks

Based on search results on the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) regarding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional research publications, 60 articles were obtained. Next, the article is downloaded in RIS (Research Information Systems) format then input into VOSViewer software and analyzed. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding Bank BTPN Syariah and Conventional

Source: Processed data, VOSViewer 1.6.18 software.

Topics were obtained, as in Figure 1 above. The results are as follows:

- Cluster 1. Red consists of 30 topics, namely: according, addition, application, bank btpn syariah, btpn, btpn syariah bank, business,

collateral, community, contract, credit, customer, discipline, documentation, economy, financing, financing product, future package, increase, interview, murabahah, observation, financing, profit, program, service, sharia principle, study, woman.

- Cluster 2. Green consists of 27 topics, namely: abstract, analysis, bank btpn syariah tbk, bopo, btpn syariah tbk, btps, company, covid, decline, dpk, financial performance, fundamental performance, indonesia, islamic bank, npf, pandemic, pbv, performance, ratio, return, roa, roe, secondary data, significant effect, stock price, variable, vecm.
- Cluster 3. Dark Blue consists of 17 topics, namely: effect, emotional intelligence, employee, employee competence, employee performance, employee productivity, high category, hypothesis, incentive, mobile banking sharia, influence, pt btpn syariah brench, research, research method, significant influence, training, value.
- Cluster 4. Yellow consists of 9 topics, namely: bank btpn syariah sidoarjo, education, effectiveness, influence, interest, perception, questionnaire, rationalization, sample.
- Cluster 5. The Color Purple consists of 9 topics, namely: pension savings bank, btpn syariah, data, data analysis, form, level, respondent, risk, tbk.
- Cluster 6. Blue consists of 7 topics, namely: capital, cost, motivation, profitability, significant positive effect, stock value, work discipline.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Financial Performance of the National Pension Savings Bank (BTPN)

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 11 topics related to BTPN's financial performance, namely:

First, the effect of profitability on the capital adequacy ratio. The effect of profitability on the capital adequacy ratio can run in two directions: (1) Increasing Profitability increases Capital Adequacy: If a bank can increase its profitability level, for example by increasing income, reducing costs, or increasing operational efficiency, then there will be the potential to generate more profits. Greater profits can increase the bank's own capital. When capital increases, the capital adequacy ratio also tends to increase, because the relative risks faced by banks in their operations can be better managed. (2) Increased Profitability reduces Capital Adequacy: On the other hand, if a bank achieves a very high level of profit but does not set aside a large portion of that profit to strengthen its capital, this can cause a decrease in the capital adequacy ratio. If capital is not commensurate with the risks faced by the bank, this can cause instability and increase the risk of bankruptcy.

Second, analyze the level of health using the CAMEL method. To analyze the health level of the National Pension Savings Bank (BTPN) using the CAMEL method, it is necessary to collect data and information related to these five criteria. The following are steps that can be taken: (1) Collect financial data: Obtain BTPN's latest financial reports, including profit and loss statements, balance sheets and cash flow reports. This data will help you in calculating the ratios needed in CAMEL analysis. (2) Capital Adequacy Evaluation (C): Calculating bank capital adequacy ratios, such as Total Capital Ratio (TCR) and Tier 1 Capital Ratio, to ensure BTPN has adequate capital. (3) Asset Quality Analysis (A): Examining the bank's credit portfolio and identifying the non-performing loan ratio, Non-Performing Loan (NPL) ratio, and other asset quality

ratios. (4) Management Quality Assessment (M): Reviewing the bank's risk management practices, internal arrangements and business strategies. Consider the experience and qualifications of key management members. (5) Earnings Performance Evaluation (E): Analyze the bank's income, net interest margin, non-interest income, and profitability within a certain time period. (6) Review Liquidity (L): Evaluate BTPN's liquidity position by checking liquidity ratios, cash reserves and the bank's ability to meet its financial obligations. (7) Comparing the results with industry standards and regulations, the results of the analysis with industry standards and regulatory requirements to assess how well BTPN performs compared to other banks.

Third, the influence of the amount of credit disbursed, Non-Performing Loans/NPL, Quality of Productive Assets/KAP, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, Operational Costs on Operating Income/BOPO, Covid-19, Murabahah financing, Musyarakah financing, and non-performing loans on profitability/Return On Assets/ROA. (1) The amount of credit disbursed is an important factor that can influence bank profitability, including ROA. The higher the amount of credit disbursed, the greater the potential for banks to earn income from interest and other costs associated with providing credit. However, an increase in the amount of credit also carries high risks, especially if the credit quality is poor and many credits fail to pay (high NPL). Therefore, although high credit can increase bank income, it must also be balanced with good risk management to avoid problem loans. (2) NPL is the percentage of total credit that borrowers are unable to pay. A high NPL level indicates that most of the credit extended by a bank cannot be recovered, which means the bank faces the risk of losing funds and decreasing profitability. When NPLs are high, banks must make adjustments by increasing reserves for credit losses and taking other actions to overcome poor credit quality. Low NPL tends to have a positive impact on ROA, because the risk of bank losses decreases, and income from credit is safer. (3) KAP is a ratio that measures the quality of a bank's productive credit portfolio. A good KAP shows that the bank has a healthier credit portfolio and the risk of credit default is lower. On the other hand, if the KAP is bad, this shows that many credits are at high risk, and it is possible that the bank will have to bear more losses due to non-performing loans. High productive asset quality tends to have a positive impact on ROA due to lower credit risk and better portfolio quality. (4) A high CAR can have a positive influence on bank profitability. With sufficient capital, BTPN can better face credit and other risks, which in turn can increase customer confidence and enable the bank to pursue more profitable business opportunities. However, it should be remembered that the nature of this influence is also influenced by other factors such as risk management policies and market conditions. (5) High FDR can have a negative influence on bank profitability. If the FDR is high, it means that the bank is highly dependent on third party funds to provide operational funds, and this can increase liquidity risk and funding costs. If banks have to pay high interest on the funds obtained, this can cause a decrease in profitability (ROA) because profit margins become narrower. (6) Low BOPO tends to have a positive influence on ROA profitability. Banks that are more efficient in managing their operational costs can increase profit margins, because most of the income generated is not used to cover high operational costs. This can increase ROA profitability at BTPN. (7) The potential impact of Covid-19 on BTPN's ROA could be: A decrease in income from interest and commissions because many customers experience financial difficulties and delay loan payments or stop making transactions. The increase in non-

performing loans is due to many debtors facing financial difficulties, thus affecting the quality of bank assets and increasing provision expenses. The decline in financing and investment volumes due to economic uncertainty resulted in lower interest and demand from customers. (8) The impact on BTPN's ROA can be varied: If Murabahah financing is successfully carried out efficiently and customers pay on time, then the bank can record profits from markups and contribute to increasing ROA. However, if there is a delay or inability of customers to pay, the quality of bank assets can be affected, causing an increase in non-performing loans and a potential decrease in ROA. (9) The effect on BTPN's ROA could be as follows: If Musyarakah financing is used for profitable and successful investments, then banks can gain profits from their share of ownership and improve ROA. However, if the project or joint investment experiences losses or fails, the bank risks bearing part of the losses, which can cause a decrease in ROA. (10) The impact on BTPN's ROA could be as follows: Non-performing loans will increase the provision burden that the bank must bear to overcome credit risk, which can reduce profitability. In addition, non-performing loans can also cause a decline in asset quality, which has a negative impact on ROA.

Fourth, management of Non-Performing Loans/NPL. The following are several general steps and strategies that BTPN can take to manage NPLs: (1) Identification of NPLs: Banks need to identify precisely and accurately the credits that fall into the NPL category. This includes analyzing the reasons why the credit went bad and assessing the possibilities for recovery. (2) Cause Analysis: BTPN must conduct an in-depth analysis of the causes of NPL, both internal and external factors. This will help to avoid NPLs in the future and improve the quality of the credit portfolio. (3) Recovery and Reconciliation: Banks must try to recover bad loans through negotiations with debtors, credit restructuring, or by using the services of special recovery agents. In some cases, this can also be done through selling collateralized assets to pay off credit. (4) Credit Restructuring: BTPN may try to restructure credit for debtors experiencing temporary financial difficulties. This involves changes in the payment schedule, interest rate, or principal amount to help the debtor overcome the problem and get back on track with payments. (5) Better Risk Management: Banks should ensure stricter risk management practices in extending credit and monitor credit portfolios continuously to avoid an increase in NPLs in the future. (6) Provisions and Reserves for Losses: Banks need to reserve a certain amount of funds to overcome potential losses due to NPLs. This is necessary to maintain the bank's financial stability and meet banking regulatory requirements. (7) Use of Technology: BTPN can utilize technology in the NPL management process. The use of algorithms and data analysis can help in identifying trends and patterns that predict potential NPLs in advance. (8) Education and Education: BTPN can also provide education and education about financial management to its customers. This can help customers be more aware of the importance of payment discipline and avoid NPLs in the future.

Fifth, the influence of capital costs, gold prices, mortgage interest, currency exchange rates and profitability on share value. (1) Cost of capital refers to the rate of return expected by shareholders or investors in return for the risks taken by investing in a company. The lower the cost of capital, the more attractive the investment in the company's shares. Factors that influence the cost of capital include interest rates, the company's perceived risk, and overall economic stability. (2) Gold prices can influence overall investor sentiment and can reflect economic instability or the global financial situation.

When gold prices rise, investors may be more inclined to invest in safe haven assets, such as precious metals, and reduce investments in stocks. Conversely, when gold prices fall, investors may be more interested in investing in stocks. (3) KPR interest can affect the housing market, and the housing sector can have an impact on banking companies such as BTPN that offer KPR products. If mortgage interest rates fall, demand for mortgages increases, and banks can experience better growth. Conversely, if mortgage interest rates rise, demand for mortgages may decline, and banks may face growth challenges. (4) Currency exchange rates can affect companies that operate on an international scale or have export/import dependencies. Companies such as BTPN that are dependent on foreign currencies may experience fluctuations in revenues and costs in local currencies due to changes in exchange rates. This can affect a company's financial performance and, consequently, the value of its shares. (5) A company's profitability is one of the main factors influencing the value of its shares. If a company records consistent profit growth and good returns for shareholders, then its shares tend to be attractive to investors. Conversely, if profitability decreases or does not meet expectations, the value of the company's shares may decrease.

Sixth, the influence of the bank's health level on dividend policy using the RGEC method (Risk Profile, Good. Corporate Governance, Earnings, Capital). When applied to Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN), the RGEC method can help bank management and shareholders to better understand the health of the bank and provide guidance in making dividend policy decisions.

Seventh, the RGEC and Altman Z- Score methods to analyze bank health and potential financial distress. (1) Implementation of RGEC involves four main aspects: Risk Profile: Evaluation of bank credit risk by analyzing asset quality and credit quality owned by the bank. Factors such as loan portfolio quality, non-performing loan (NPL) level, and other credit risks are evaluated here. Good Corporate Governance (GCG): Assess the bank's corporate governance, including internal control systems and risk management practices. The efficiency and transparency of company management are considered key indicators in this regard. Earnings: Analysis of bank income and profitability. Factors considered include the profit-to-assets ratio (ROA), profit-to-equity ratio (ROE), and the bank's ability to generate sustainable income. Capital: Assessing the bank's capital level to ensure capital adequacy to face credit and operational risks. Capital adequacy ratios, such as the ratio of core capital to risk-weighted assets (Capital Adequacy Ratio), are an important factor in this assessment. (2) Altman Z-Score is a predictive model used to measure the potential bankruptcy of a company. This model can also be applied to financial institutions such as banks to assess the possibility of financial distress. The following factors are used in calculating the Altman Z-Score: Working Capital/Total Assets: Measures liquidity and the proportion of company assets that are expected to be easily converted into cash to meet short-term obligations. Retained Earnings/Total Assets: Assesses the extent to which the company has accumulated profits that indicate stability and the ability to invest in growth. Earnings Before Interest and Taxes (EBIT)/Total Assets: Assess the company's profitability without taking into account interest and tax costs. Market Value of Equity/Book Value of Total Liabilities: Measures the market value of a company's equity compared to the total liabilities recorded on the balance sheet. Sales/Total Assets: Measures the company's efficiency in using its assets to generate sales.

Eighth, the influence of Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE on the Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. (1) The higher the ROA, the greater the bank's potential to generate profits from the assets it owns. This will contribute to increasing capital and in turn can increase the bank's CAR. Banks that are efficient in managing their assets tend to have better CARs because the profits generated can be used to increase capital. (2) A high level of ROE indicates that the bank generates quite large profits for shareholders relative to the equity owned. If the bank can maintain a high ROE and manage risk well, then the profits generated can be used to increase capital and ultimately increase CAR.

Ninth, the influence of Non Performing Financing/NPF and Third Party Funds/DPK on the Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR. (1) A high NPF level can be a sign of bank asset quality problems, and this can affect the bank's liquidity and profitability. If BTPN's NPF level increases, the bank will face a higher risk of default and possibly incur financial losses. This could cause banks to be more cautious in providing new financing, which in turn could affect FDR growth. (2) DPK is important for banks because it is the main source of funds to provide financing. The higher the DPK, the more funds available for banks to provide financing. If BTPN's DPK increases, the bank will have more funds that can be used for financing, and this could have a positive impact on FDR. Conversely, if TPF decreases, banks may need to look for other sources of funds, such as loans from other banks or financial institutions, which can affect FDR.

Tenth, the influence of profitability on profit growth. There are several ways in which profitability can influence profit growth at Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional: (1) Increased Income: If BTPN is able to increase its profitability, for example by increasing income from sources such as loan interest, transaction fees, etc., this can contribute to higher profit growth. (2) Cost Control: If BTPN succeeds in reducing its operational costs or increasing efficiency, this can increase profitability, which in turn has the potential to influence profit growth by increasing profit margins. (3) Business Expansion: Strong profitability can provide BTPN with more resources to expand its business into new regions or sectors. In this case, successful expansion can contribute to overall profit growth. (4) Improving Asset Quality: High profitability can give BTPN the ability to more easily deal with asset quality problems, such as bad credit. By addressing these issues, banks can reduce associated losses and influence profit growth positively. (5) Technology and Innovation Investment: With sufficient profits, BTPN can more easily invest in technology and innovation. These changes can improve operational efficiency and give banks a competitive advantage, which can ultimately have a positive impact on profit growth.

Eleventh, financial performance based on spin-offs, mergers and acquisitions. (1) The impact of spin-offs on BTPN's financial performance may vary: Focus benefits: Spin-offs allow new companies to focus more on their core business, which can improve operational efficiency and financial performance. Risk reduction: Spin-offs can reduce the operational and financial risks of the spun-off business, which in turn can have a positive impact on BTPN's overall performance. Liquidity potential: If the spun-off company is successful, BTPN shareholders may acquire new shares as part of the spin-off transaction, which could increase the value of their portfolio. (2) The impact of the merger on BTPN's financial performance may include: Operational synergies: Through the merger, BTPN can achieve synergies that increase efficiency, reduce operational costs and increase profits. Increased market share: By combining resources with other companies, BTPN can expand market share and increase revenue

potential. Integration risks: Mergers can pose complex integration risks and high costs. If the integration process does not run smoothly, BTPN's financial performance could be negatively affected. (3) The impact of acquisitions on BTPN's financial performance may include: Business diversification: Acquisitions can help BTPN expand its business reach into new market segments or different regions. Revenue growth potential: Through acquisitions, BTPN can access new customers and increase revenue. Financial burden: If the acquisition is carried out using debt, BTPN may experience an increase in financial burden which could affect profitability.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Performance of National Pension Savings Bank (BTPN) Employees

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 23 topics related to BTPN employee performance, namely: (1) Transformational leadership style; (2) Work environment; (3) Work Discipline; (4) Communication; (5) Financial and non-financial compensation; (6) Change management; (7) Competence; (8) Work motivation; (9) Career development; (10) Punishment/discipline; (11) Job stress; (12) Knowledge management; (13) Locus of control; (14) Labor recruitment process; (15) Providing incentives; (16) Rewards; (17) Self-efficacy; (18) Awards; (19) Training; (20) Resilience; (21) Employee engagement; (22) Organizational culture; and (23) Teamwork.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Customer Behavior at Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN)

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 25 topics related to BTPN customer behavior, namely: (1) Customer relationship marketing; (2) Service quality; (3) Credit services; (4) Social marketing; (5) Income; (6) Brand positioning dimensions; (7) Interest rates; (8) Trust; (9) Brand; (10) Good Corporate Governance/GCG; (11) Social interaction via Instagram; (12) Post power syndrome; (13) E-business; (14) Company image; (15) Promotion; (16) Digitalization; (17) English expressions; (18) Perception of the Huraba community; (19) Mobile banking genius; (20) Personal selling; (21) Convenience; (22) Perceived benefits; (23) Experience; (24) Commitment; and (25) Marketing communications.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Financing Credit Products at the National Pension Savings Bank (BTPN)

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 17 topics related to financing credit products at BTPN, namely:

First, risk management and mitigation to minimize the risk of credit/problem credit/bad credit. To minimize the risk of problematic or bad credit, BPTN will carry out a careful credit assessment process before providing loans to customers. This credit analysis will include evaluating the customer's suitability for repaying the loan based on data such as credit history, income and assets owned. Apart from that, BPTN will also set a maximum limit on the amount of loan that can be given to one customer so that risks are diversified and not too concentrated on one party.

Second, credit granting factors: bank funds, debtor income, interest rates. (1) Bank Funds: BPTN will consider the availability of funds it has to provide credit. The amount of funds that can be loaned will depend on the bank's liquidity and credit capacity. (2) Debtor's Income: A customer's ability to repay a loan is greatly influenced by their income. The higher their income, the

greater their ability to pay loan installments. (3) Interest Rate: The interest rate will affect the amount of installment payments that the customer must make. The interest rate set usually follows central bank policy and the level of risk associated with the loan.

Third, resolving bad/problematic credit. When problematic or bad credit occurs, BPTN will try to resolve this problem using various approaches. Banks will usually communicate with customers to find solutions, such as credit restructuring or extending payment terms. If an amicable settlement is not successful, BPTN has the right to take legal action to collect receivables or sell collateral provided by the customer as collateral.

Fourth, guarantee/collateral in financing, in the form of copyright. Collateral is an asset used by a customer as collateral to obtain a loan. If the customer cannot fulfill payment obligations, the bank has the right to take and sell the collateral to cover losses from non-performing loans. Copyright can be a form of collateral, especially if the customer is the copyright owner of a work that has commercial value.

Fifth, productive financing credit, such as motor vehicles. BPTN also provides credit for productive financing, such as motor vehicles. This kind of credit is used to finance vehicle purchases that can support the customer's productivity or business. For example, for entrepreneurs or corporate members, motorized vehicles may be needed to support business operations. In this case, the vehicle can be used as collateral by the bank to provide a loan at the appropriate interest rate. If the customer cannot pay the credit on time, the bank has the right to take the vehicle as collateral and sell it to cover the unpaid obligations.

Sixth, the influence of Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR and Return On Assets/ROA on credit distribution. (1) Influence of CAR on credit distribution at BPTN: If BPTN has a low CAR, it means that the bank's capital is also low so the possibility of distributing large-scale credit will be limited. Conversely, if the CAR is high, banks will have more confidence in disbursing credit because they have the ability to bear greater credit risk. (2) The effect of ROA on credit distribution at BPTN: A high ROA indicates that BPTN has succeeded in generating significant profits from its assets. This gives the bank more funds that can be used to distribute credit to customers, because the bank believes that lending will provide good returns and contribute to higher profits.

Seventh, the effect of providing credit on company profits. The effect of providing credit on company profits can be explained as follows: (1) Increasing credit provision: If BPTN increases the amount of credit given to customers carefully and appropriately, this can increase the bank's potential income. Interest and fees received from customers who lend money can be the main source of income for banks. (2) Credit risk: Although providing credit can increase income, banks must also pay attention to credit risk. If poor credit quality and credit defaults increase, banks will experience losses, which will impact company profits. (3) Credit management efficiency: Banks must have an efficient credit management process to minimize the risk of default and increase income. Careful credit evaluation, regular monitoring of credit quality, and efforts to recover bad credit are some of the important steps that banks must take.

Eighth, implementation of the Mudharabah contract profit sharing system. The application of the Mudharabah contract profit sharing system in the context of the National Savings Bank (BPTN) refers to sharia principles in its operations. Mudharabah is a form of cooperation agreement between two

parties, namely BPTN as the capital owner and the customer as the capital manager. In this contract, profits are shared based on a previous agreement, while losses are borne by the capital owner (BPTN) unless the loss is caused by error or negligence on the part of the capital manager. In the context of implementing Mudharabah, BPTN will provide capital to customers (for example in the form of savings or investments), and customers will use this capital for certain businesses or investments. The profits generated from the business or investment are then shared between BPTN and the customer according to the initial agreement. The implementation of the Mudharabah contract profit sharing system is in accordance with Islamic economic principles which encourage fairness in the distribution of profits and risks between the parties involved in economic transactions.

Ninth, the Future Package/PMD financing program for women/mothers. The Future Package Financing Program (PMD) is a financing program offered by BPTN, especially for women or mothers. The aim of this program is to provide financial support to women so they can develop businesses or meet other financial needs that contribute to a better future. PMD can include various types of financing such as business loans, working capital financing, investment financing, and other financial products that suit the needs of women/mothers. This program is usually designed with special requirements and offers that accommodate the needs and conditions of women as target recipients of financing. By providing financial support through the PMD program, BPTN hopes to encourage women's economic independence and their contribution to the wider economy.

Tenth, Murabahah and Wakalah financing according to Muamalah fiqh. (1) Murabahah: Murabahah is a form of financing in Islam where a bank or financial institution buys goods desired by the customer and resells them at a pre-agreed price. The customer pays the price in installments over a certain period. This is in accordance with the principles of Muamalah jurisprudence which prohibits usury (interest). (2) Wakalah: Wakalah is a mechanism in Islamic financing where the customer authorizes the bank or financial institution to carry out actions on his behalf, for example in arranging the purchase and sale of financed goods. The bank acts as a representative and receives compensation for its services. This principle is also in accordance with Muamalah fiqh which prioritizes the principle of justice and not violating sharia rules.

Eleventh, the influence of credit provision and supervision on the effectiveness of business credit. Providing appropriate credit and good supervision will have a positive impact on the effectiveness of business credit. If banks provide credit carefully to prospective borrowers who are eligible, the risk of bad credit can be minimized. In addition, close monitoring of the use of credit funds will prevent misuse of funds and help ensure that credit is used for its intended purposes. In this way, the effectiveness of business credit increases, and opportunities for customers to develop become better.

Twelfth, administration of financing applications. Administration of financing applications includes the process of collecting and evaluating the documents required from prospective borrowers. This involves an assessment of creditworthiness, including analysis of a potential borrower's financial, credit history, and risk profile. This process also includes determining the type of financing that best suits the customer's needs. Good administration will ensure that the application process runs smoothly, transparently and efficiently for all parties involved.

Thirteenth, AHP and SAW methods for productive financing. (1) AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process): AHP is a method used to make decisions by considering different criteria and sub-criteria. In productive financing, AHP can be used to help banks assess financing alternatives based on a number of criteria, such as risk, profit potential and social impact. (2) SAW (Simple Additive Weighting): SAW is another method used to make decisions by giving weight to each criterion and calculating the total score for each alternative. In the context of productive financing, SAW can assist in selecting the most appropriate financing alternative based on the relative assessment of each criterion.

Fourteenth, credit feasibility decision support system. A creditworthiness decision support system is a tool or platform that assists financial institutions in assessing the feasibility of extending credit to customers. These systems are usually based on analytical models that combine financial data, credit history and other factors to assess a customer's credit risk and ability to repay a loan. With this decision support system, the assessment process can be carried out faster, more objectively and more accurately.

Fifteenth, implementation of Bai' Bitsaman Ajil/BBA. Bai' Bitsaman Ajil (BBA) is a buying and selling transaction in Islamic financing where a bank or financial institution sells goods to customers at a deferred cash price. This means that customers can pay the price of goods in installments over a certain period of time. In the context of financing, BBA can be used to help customers obtain the goods they need without violating sharia principles which prohibit usury.

Sixteenth, the influence of Murabahah financing on the welfare of Muslim customers. Murabahah financing, because it is in accordance with sharia principles, can have a positive impact on the welfare of Muslim customers. By using this financing, customers can obtain goods or capital needed for business or other purposes without having to pay usury interest. This can reduce financial burdens and provide a sense of security and legal certainty for customers. In the long term, if this financing is used wisely and responsibly, it can help improve the financial welfare of Muslim customers.

Seventeenth, the effect of financing on increasing customer income. Financing provided by banks or financial institutions can have an impact on increasing customer income if the financing is used for productive investments, such as businesses or projects that have the potential to generate greater income. With financing, customers can access capital that may previously have been difficult to obtain, so they have the opportunity to develop larger and more profitable businesses or projects. However, the final result will depend on how the customer manages the financing and runs the business or project well.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Savings Products at the National Pension Savings Bank (BTPN)

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 2 topics related to savings products at BTPN, namely:

First, the influence of deposit interest rates on the amount of time deposit funds. When deposit interest rates rise, this tends to increase the attractiveness of deposits as an investment instrument because customers will get greater profits from the funds they place. As a result, funds placed in time deposits at BTPN or other financial institutions can increase, because people are more inclined to save or invest in deposits with more profitable rates of return. Conversely, if deposit interest rates fall, the attractiveness of deposits as an

investment instrument will also decrease, and customers may look for investment alternatives with higher rates of return. This may result in a decrease in the amount of funds placed in time deposits at BPTN or other financial institutions. It is important for BPTN to monitor and adjust deposit interest rates carefully in accordance with market conditions and monetary policy objectives. By setting deposit interest rates appropriately, BPTN can attract more term deposit funds, which in turn can be used to provide financing in various banking and financial activities.

Second, the information technology in mobile banking is genius. The information technology used in Jenius mobile banking includes various features and services such as: (1) Innovative Mobile Application: Jenius has an intuitive and user-friendly user interface. This application allows customers to access their accounts, make fund transfers, view transaction history, and set various banking preferences. (2) Personal Financial Management: Jenius offers a variety of financial management tools that help customers understand and manage their spending. Features such as "Dream Saver" allow customers to set savings targets and manage budgets more effectively. (3) Smart Savings Feature: Jenius provides an automatic savings feature that allows customers to set up automatic transfers to their savings accounts every time they make certain transactions, such as bill payments or purchases. (4) Digital Debit Card: Jenius allows customers to make digital payments via a virtual debit card that can be integrated with popular digital wallet applications. (5) International Transactions: Jenius supports international transactions with transparent fees and can be accessed via the mobile banking application.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Other Issues at the National Pension Savings Bank (BTPN)

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 6 research topics related to issues at BTPN, namely:

First, legal protection from fraud and phishing in the banking world. BPTN will have a dedicated cyber security team to proactively identify and address security threats. In addition, they will provide education to customers on how to identify and avoid phishing attempts. Legal protection can also include provisions in agreements with customers that state the bank's responsibility in certain cases of unavoidable fraud.

Second, the cash disbursement system. BPTN will use a sophisticated and integrated cash disbursement system to ensure that all transactions leaving the bank are carried out correctly, efficiently and in accordance with applicable banking rules and regulations. The system will also observe strict security measures to prevent misuse of funds and fraudulent attempts.

Third, savings and loan accounting application. By adopting the savings and loan accounting application, BPTN can increase operational efficiency and improve services to customers. This application also helps banks in credit supervision and risk management, thereby reducing potential credit risks that banks may face.

Fourth, predict stock prices using the ARIMA and GARCH models. BPTN can utilize ARIMA and GARCH models to carry out stock price analysis to understand patterns and trends in stock price movements in the past. In this way, banks can make stock price predictions to help make investment decisions or manage portfolios for customers who invest in the stock market.

Fifth, factors that influence the occurrence of fraud. The occurrence of fraud in banking can be influenced by various factors. Several factors that can

influence the risk of fraud include: (1) Weaknesses in the bank's security and supervision systems. (2) Bank employees or internal parties who are dishonest or involved in fraudulent acts. (3) The presence of security gaps in the IT system that can be exploited by irresponsible parties. (4) Non-compliance or negligence in implementing established security procedures. (5) Changes in the economic or social environment that influence individual behavior.

Sixth, fundamental and technical analysis of shares. (1) Fundamental Analysis: This analysis focuses on assessing the intrinsic value of shares by exploring data and information about the company's financial performance, business prospects, management, and macroeconomic factors that can influence share prices. This method is more directed towards long-term investment by considering the quality of the company. (2) Technical Analysis: This approach involves analyzing stock price charts and trading volume to identify historical patterns and stock price trends. By analyzing these patterns, technical analysis attempts to predict the future direction of stock prices. This method is more often used by short-term traders who focus on price fluctuations and market momentum.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Pension Funds at the National Pension Savings Bank (BTPN)

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 4 topics related to pension funds at BTPN, namely:

First, the mechanism and management of sharia pension funds. In managing sharia pension funds, BTPN will manage these funds in accordance with sharia principles, such as the prohibition of usury (interest), speculation, and investment in businesses prohibited by the Islamic religion. BTPN will invest in instruments that are halal and ethically profitable, such as company shares that do not conflict with sharia principles, sharia bonds, and so on. The main objective of sharia pension fund management is to provide benefits for retirees while still complying with sharia principles.

Second, the control system for granting pension credits. In this system, BTPN will determine eligibility requirements for granting credit to retirees. Factors usually considered include the age of the retiree, the size of the pension funds received, credit history, and repayment capacity. Strict controls are implemented to ensure that credit provision is carried out responsibly and does not pose a high credit risk.

Third, guarantee/collateral in financing, in the form of a pension certificate. A pension certificate is an official document issued by a pension agency (for example, Taspen and ASABRI) which states the amount of pension funds received by retirees each month. This document serves as a guarantee that the retiree has a steady income from the pension and can be used as collateral to support an application for financing or credit.

Fourth, the Taspen Mobile and ASABRI applications for membership and claiming pension funds. Taspen Mobile and ASABRI are applications related to pension institutions in Indonesia, namely TASPEN (Taspen Persero) and ASABRI (Social Insurance for the Armed Forces of the Republic of Indonesia). This application focuses on participation and claiming pension funds for eligible participants. Taspen Mobile and ASABRI allow pension participants to access information related to their pension funds, including viewing balances, payment details and other details. Participants can monitor the development of their pension funds through this application. When a pension participant dies, his or her heirs can use the Taspen Mobile and ASABRI applications to submit a claim

for pension funds. This process is carried out online via an application, which makes the claim process easier and faster for the heirs.

Mapping Research Topics using Literature Study regarding Other Issues at the National Pension Savings Bank (BTPN)

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 7 research topics related to issues at BTPN, namely:

First, legal protection from fraud and phishing in the banking world. Bank Pensiunan Tabungan Nasional (BPTN) will provide legal protection to its customers against acts of fraud and phishing that occur in the banking world. Fraud is an act of deception or cheating that aims to obtain illegal profits or harm other parties. Phishing is a hacking attempt that uses social techniques to obtain sensitive information such as passwords, credit card numbers or other personal data. To protect customers from fraud, BPTN will implement various layers of security. This includes advanced security technology, suspicious transaction monitoring, and early detection systems to recognize unusual activity. Apart from that, BPTN will also provide education to customers about potential risks and how to avoid fraud and phishing. If a customer becomes a victim of fraud or phishing, BPTN will provide assistance and assistance to resolve the problem. In addition, BPTN will cooperate with law enforcement authorities to follow up and investigate the perpetrators of these crimes.

Second, the cash disbursement system. The cash disbursement system at Bank Pensiunan Tabungan Nasional (BPTN) refers to the mechanism used by the bank to regulate and monitor the process of withdrawing money from customer accounts. Customers can make cash withdrawals through ATMs, bank branches, or using digital banking services. The cash disbursement process at BPTN is usually carried out using a debit card or ATM card issued by the bank. Customers will be asked to enter a PIN (Personal Identification Number) as valid identification before they can make a spending transaction. BPTN will also implement additional security measures to protect customers from fraudulent activities or unauthorized card use. This includes transaction verification via OTP (One-Time Password) codes or other authentication methods.

Third, savings and loan accounting application. The Savings and Loans Accounting Application at Bank Pensiunan Tabungan Nasional (BPTN) is a system used to record, manage and track savings and loan transactions made by customers. This application helps banks manage customer financial activities efficiently and accurately. This application will record every savings transaction carried out by the customer, such as cash deposits, transfers, or interest received. Apart from that, this application will also record customer loan transactions, including loan amount, term, interest rate and payment schedule. By using a savings and loan accounting application, BPTN can produce comprehensive financial reports and analysis of loan portfolio performance. This allows banks to monitor customers' financial health and identify potential risks in providing loans.

Fourth, predict stock prices using the ARIMA and GARCH models. Stock price prediction using the ARIMA (AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average) and GARCH (Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity) models is a statistical method used to analyze and predict stock price movements in the financial market. Bank Pensiunan Tabungan Nasional (BPTN) can use this model as part of their investment strategy and portfolio management. By analyzing historical stock price data, the ARIMA model can identify trends and

patterns of stock price movements in the past. Meanwhile, the GARCH model is used to overcome stock price volatility which changes over time. By predicting stock prices, BPTN can make smarter investment decisions and provide recommendations to their customers regarding potentially profitable stock investments.

Fifth, factors that influence the occurrence of fraud. These include: (1) Security System Weaknesses: If BPTN's security system is not strong enough or has loopholes, fraudsters can easily steal customers' personal information or financial data to commit fraud. (2) Lack of Customer Education and Awareness: Customers who are less educated about banking security risks tend to be more vulnerable to becoming victims of fraud. Customer education and awareness about common fraud tactics can help prevent fraud. (3) Internal Collusion or Dishonest Employees: Fraud can also occur if there is collusion between internal bank parties who are dishonest or lack integrity, who take advantage of their position to commit fraud. (4) Financial Pressure or Financial Motivation: Some fraud perpetrators are driven by urgent personal financial problems and look for illegal ways to overcome these problems. (5) Bad System or Process Changes: If BPTN experiences system or process changes that are not properly monitored, fraudsters can take advantage of this situation to carry out criminal acts. To reduce the risk of fraud, BPTN needs to implement strict security policies, provide education for customers, carefully verify and validate transactions, and closely monitor employee activities.

Sixth, fundamental and technical analysis of shares. (1) Stock Fundamental Analysis: Stock fundamental analysis involves assessing the intrinsic value of a stock based on the company's financial performance and fundamentals. For BPTN as a bank, this means analyzing financial reports, profit growth, financial ratios, company management, industry prospects, and other economic factors that can influence the bank's performance and its share price. (2) Stock Technical Analysis: Stock technical analysis focuses on the historical price movements of stocks and their trading volumes to identify patterns and trends that can help in making investment decisions. This analysis involves using charts, technical indicators, and other tools to understand market behavior and try to predict the next direction of stock prices. Bank Pensiunan Tabungan Nasional (BPTN) can use both of these methods to inform their investment decisions and provide advice to their customers about the potential for profitable stock investments.

Seventh, assistance to MSME customers. Bank Pensiunan Tabungan Nasional (BPTN) can provide special assistance programs to Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise (MSME) customers to help them develop their businesses. This assistance may include: (1) Financial Consultation: Providing financial advice to MSME owners to better manage business finances and help them create effective financial plans. (2) Training and Development: Providing special training or workshops to improve the skills and knowledge of MSME owners in managing their businesses, including management, marketing and business strategy. (3) Access to Financing: Helping MSME owners gain access to financing sources that suit their business needs. (4) Networks and Connections: Facilitate meetings and collaboration between MSME owners and other parties in the bank network or business partnerships that can benefit their business growth. (5) Monitoring and Evaluation: Carrying out regular monitoring and evaluation of the business progress of the MSMEs being assisted, so that BPTN can provide more appropriate assistance according to their needs. It is hoped that assistance to MSME customers can help MSMEs improve their business performance,

strengthen the local economy, and contribute to the country's overall economic growth.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 6 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding Sharia and Conventional BPTN, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing credit products; (5) Savings products; and (6) Other issues.

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan*

- Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Kompetensi (Competence : Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>

- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): *JEMPER Januari-Juni*, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>

- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>